

Effects of Jigsaw and Geoboard Instructional Strategies on Students' Attitude Towards Geometry in Delta State

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ABSTRACT

The study investigated the effects of Jigsaw and Geoboard Instructional Strategies on geometry Students' attitude towards geometry. Two research questions and two hypothesis were formulated to guide this study. The study adopted the quasi-experimental (non - randomized, pre-test, post-test, planned variation) design. The population of the study consisted of 18,879 SSII mathematics students in 435 public secondary schools in Delta State. The sample for the study consisted of 289 SSII students drawn from six public mixed secondary schools, using simple random sampling. Two from each of the three Senatorial Districts of the state. The Geometry Attitude Questionnaire (GAQ) contained twenty (20) items that seeks the opinion of students on the effects of jigsaw instruction and Geoboard instructional Strategies on students' attitude towards Geometry was adopted as the major instrument for the study. On analysis, a reliability coefficient of 0.88 was obtained. Both the experimental and control groups were pretested with the 50 items Mathematics Achievement Test (MAT) and 20 items Mathematics Attitude Questionnaire (MAQ). Descriptive statistics as was used as method of data analysis in order to answer the research questions raised. This involved the use of mean and standard deviation. The testing of null hypotheses involved the use of t-test and Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) as well as Shefe post hoc tetst. Hypothesis testing was done at 0.05 level of significance Findings from the results showed that Jigsaw teaching, Geoboard strategy have significant effects on students attitude towards geometry. Based on the findings of this study, the researcher therefore recommend the adoption of jigsaw teaching strategy by mathematics teachers when there is special need to students' positive attitude towards geometry. Mathematics teachers should attend workshops to get acquainted with innovative instructional strategies. And Mathematics teachers should strive to ensure that students are active during instruction as this will help to stimulate their interest in having a better attitude towards geometry.

Introduction

Mathematics is a *siqua non* for the prosperity of any Nation. It is the basics for understanding science, engineering, technology and economics. It is an important tool for public decision making and for engaging in the knowledge economy. The branches of mathematics include Number & Numeration, Geometry, Mensuration, Trigonometry and Statistics (Akpokiniovo, 2022). Among these branches, geometry is one of the branch that is taught across the different levels of our educational system, from primary to tertiary level and also across different disciplines. Geometry therefore, should be given proper attention in terms of teaching at the school. The application of geometry to aviation dated back to five thousand years ago by the Egyptian surveyors with the skills of measurement of lengths, areas, angles, bearing and Pythagorean triple. Designing a plan and production of a well designed building by architects, artisans and engineers, is hinged on the knowledge of properties of shapes, measurement of lengths, construction of shapes, calculation of areas and volumes. Furthermore, the skills of bearing are of utmost importance in the aviation industry for efficient and effective operation (Akaazua, Bolaji, Kajuru, Mu, Musa, and Bala 2017).

Despite the importance of geometry and its usefulness in everyday life as an aspect of Mathematics, students still perform poorly in mathematics particularly in geometry (Celik, 2018). This can be traced back to students' memorization of geometrical concepts as a result of poor teaching methods used by Mathematics teachers at the secondary school level. Thus, the lecture technique is one of the most commonly used teacher-centred approaches. The lecture method of instruction is a teacher-centred approach in which the teacher passes on knowledge in its ultimate form to the students (Akpokiniovo, 2018). The major job of the teacher is to assist and guide students in their learning and overall grasp of information (Jegede and Awodun , 2015). Under the leadership of the teacher, the students take charge of their own learning having a good attitude towards the subject. Jigsaw and Geoboard seems to enhance students' achievements and attitude in Mathematics.

Jigsaw instructional strategy is a method of organizing classroom learning in such a way that lesson contents are broken down into pieces, and the class subdivided into groups of about three to five students depending on the class size, and students are dependent on each other to complete the jigsaw puzzle (Ijeh, 2013). Therefore the significance of the use of jigsaw instructional strategy has not been tested using geometry as a mathematical concept and is yet to be concluded. Therefore, there is need to find out if Jigsaw instructional strategy could have effect on students' attitude in geometry. There is also the need to also examine the use of geoboard as another student-centred teaching strategy.

Geoboard is a short form for geometrical board. According to Russel (2013), Geoboard as a manipulative that is used to support learning of geometry, measurement and numeracy. A Geoboard is made up of piece of wood and some nails. It can be used to demonstrate the properties of plane shapes, it is also useful in the study of area and perimeter of plane shapes. Ruseel also describes Geoboard as a rectangular board with nails nailed into its surfaces in such a way, with equal intervals in between. Rubber bands and threads are used to connect the number of nails needed to form appropriate concept(s) such as perimeters and lengths, in using the geoboard for the teaching of geometry. Despite the fact that geoboard has been recommended for teaching and learning of geometric theorems, its effectiveness has not been experimentally and conclusively determined as regards to student academic attitude.

Eagly and Chaiken (2007), defined attitude as a psychological propensity that is conveyed by a positive or negative evaluation of a certain entity. The opinion and feeling you have about anything is referred to as your attitude. Attitude is typically characterized as a favourable or unfavourable attitude to a subject, person, or an event. Academic accomplishment and a good study pattern are greatly influenced by one's attitude toward studying (Achor and Kalu, 2014). Regardless of students' sex, Jigsaw and Geobaord instructional Strategies may improve students' attitudes toward numerous subjects. This study sought to examine the effects of Jigsaw and Geobaord instructional Strategies on secondary school geometry students' attitude in Delta State.

Statement of the Problem

Student performance in geometry is decreasing, the use of the lecture method is believed to have made students in Nigerian secondary schools resort to memorizing of mathematics principles as a result of their passive involvement in the teaching and learning process. The students in the lecture classroom are not given the opportunity to perform learning task, attempts to monitor, regulate and control their cognition. These explained the reason why students have phobia and bad attitude especially when going for mathematics examination. This calls for the adoption of students-centred teaching methods such as jigsaw teaching and geobaord instructional Strategies that gives students opportunity to set goals for their learning, perform learning task(s) and attempts to monitor, regulate and control their cognition and have a better attitude towards geometry. Hence, the problem of this study is: What is the effect of jigsaw and geoboard teaching strategies on students' attitude towards geometry? The question gives rise to the study.

Research Questions

The following questions were formulated to direct this study:

1. What is the effect of jigsaw teaching strategy, geoboard instructional strategy and lecture method on students' attitude towards geometry?
2. What is the difference in the geometry mean attitude scores among students taught with jigsaw teaching strategy, geoboard instructional strategy and lecture method?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance:

1. There is no significant effect of jigsaw teaching strategy, geoboard instructional strategy and lecture method on students' attitude towards Geometry.
2. There is no significant difference in the geometry mean attitude scores among students taught with jigsaw teaching strategy, geoboard instructional strategy and lecture method

Methods of the Study

The study adopted quasi-experimental design. Specifically, the pretest, posttest planned variation design was used. In this design, random assignment of subjects to experimental and control groups was not used rather intact class was used in order not to disrupt classroom teaching. The population of the study will comprise all public Senior Secondary School Mathematics students in Delta State. Specifically, the study population consists of 18,879 SSII Mathematics students in public Secondary Schools in Delta State. A sample of two hundred and eighty nine (289) SSII Mathematics students selected from six (6) public mixed senior secondary schools in Delta State was used as the sample size for this study. Simple random sampling technique was used to select the 6 schools. Specifically, the researcher randomly selected two schools each from the three Senatorial Districts of Delta State. The Geometry Attitude Questionnaire (GAQ) contained twenty (20) items that seeks the opinion of students on the effects of jigsaw instruction and Geoboard instructional Strategies on students' attitude towards Geometry was adopted as the major instrument for the study. The responses to the Geometry Attitude questionnaire was framed on a 4-point-likert scale of Strongly Agreed (SA = 4), Agreed (A = 3), Disagreed (D = 2) and Strongly Disagreed (SD = 1). The reliability of the Geometry Attitude Questionnaire (GAQ) was established using the Cronbach-Alpha technique. The instrument (MAQ) was administered to 40 Mathematics students in another Public Secondary School in Oredo Local Government Area of Edo State which was outside the sampled schools for this study. The responses of the 40 students were scored and the obtained scores were subjected to the Cronbach-Alpha analysis using Statistical Packages for Social Sciences (SPSS). On analysis, a reliability coefficient of 0.88 was

obtained. Both the experimental and control groups were pretested with the 50 items Mathematics Achievement Test (MAT) and 20 items Mathematics Attitude Questionnaire (MAQ). This was carried out to determine the equivalence of the groups before treatment and be sure that any noticed change later is due to treatment. On treatment for the control group, each and all the contents in the six week instructional unit were presented to the students using lecture method. At the expirations of the six weeks treatment, students in both experimental and control groups were posttested with the 20 items MAQ after re-shuffling the items and scored. Students’ scores in the experimental and control groups from the pretest and posttest was collated, analysed and compared in a bid to ascertain the effects of jigsaw teaching and Geobaord instructional Strategies on geometry students’ attitude. Descriptive statistics as was used as method of data analysis in order to answer the research questions raised. This involved the use of mean and standard deviation. The testing of null hypotheses involved the use of t-test and Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) as well as Shefe post hoc tetst. Hypothesis testing was done at 0.05 level of significance.

Results and Discussion

The results are tabulated and interpreted immediately after each table according to the research questions and corresponding hypotheses.

Research Question One: What is the effect of jigsaw teaching strategy, geoboard instructional strategy and lecture method on students’ attitude towards geometry?

Table 1: Mean and Standard Deviation of Pretest and Posttest Attitude Scores among Students Taught Geometry Using Jigsaw Teaching Strategy, Geoboard Strategy and Lecture Method

Group	N	Pretest Mean	SD	Posttest Mean	SD	Mean Difference
Jigsaw teaching strategy	99	24.16	8.91	57.78	11.63	33.62
Geoboard strategy	97	22.93	5.40	44.29	8.13	21.36
Lecture	93	22.77	7.70	43.46	10.12	20.69
Total	289					

The data in Table 1 shows a pretest mean attitude scores of 24.16, 22.93 and 22.77, and standard deviation of 8.91, 5.40 and 7.70, for students in the jigsaw teaching strategy, Geoboard strategy and lecture method groups. A higher posttest mean attitude scores of 57.78, 44.29 and 43.46, and standard deviation of 11.63, 8.13 and 10.12, was recorded respectively for students in the jigsaw teaching strategy, geobaord strategy and lecture method groups. The observed increment of 33.62, 21.36 and 20.69, for students in the jigsaw teaching strategy, geoboard strategy and lecture method groups is not due to chance rather as a result of treatment. This implies that jigsaw teaching strategy, geoboard strategy and lecture method have effect on students’ attitude towards geometry.

Hypotheses One: There is no significant effect of jigsaw teaching strategy, geoboard instructional strategy and lecture method on students’ attitude towards Geometry.

Table 2: t-test Comparison of Pretest and Posttest Mean Attitude Scores of Students Taught Goemetry using Jigsaw Teaching Strategy, Geoboard Strategy and Lecture Method

Group	N	Pre-test Mean	SD	Posttest Mean	SD	df	t-cal	sig. (2-tailed)	Remark
Jigsaw	99	24.16	8.91	57.78	11.63	98	34.48	0.00	Ho ₅ is rejected
Geoboard	97	22.93	5.40	44.29	8.13	96	18.92	0.00	
Lecture	93	22.77	7.70	43.46	10.12	92	20.91	0.00	
Total	289								

P<0.05

Table 2 indicates a significant effect of jigsaw teaching strategy ($t = 34.48, P(0.00) < 0.05$), geobaord strategy ($t = 18.92, P(0.00) < 0.05$), and lecture method ($t = 20.91, P(0.00) < 0.05$) on attitude. Therefore, Ho₅ was rejected. Thus, there is a significant effect of jigsaw teaching strategy, geobaord strategy and lecture method on students’ attitude towards geometry.

Research Question Two: What is the difference in the geometry mean attitude scores among students taught with jigsaw teaching strategy, geoboard instructional strategy and lecture method?

Table 3: Mean and Standard Deviation of Pretest and Posttest Attitude Scores among Students Taught Geometry Using Jigsaw Teaching Strategy, Geoboard Strategy and Lecture Method

Group	N	Pretest		posttest		Mean Difference
		Mean	SD	Mean	SD	
Jigsaw strategy	99	24.16	8.91	57.78	11.63	33.62
Geoboard strategy	97	22.93	5.40	44.29	8.13	21.36
Lecture method	93	22.77	7.70	43.46	10.12	20.69
Total	289					

The data in Table 3 shows a pretest mean attitude scores of 24.16, 22.93 and 22.77, for students taught geometry using jigsaw teaching strategy, geoboard strategy and lecture method. This implies that all the groups were not at equivalent on their attitude towards geometry before treatment by mere comparison of the means. Although students in the jigsaw teaching strategy group had a slightly higher pretest mean attitude score than their counterparts in geoboard strategy and lecture method groups. For the posttest, the experimental groups (jigsaw teaching and geoboard strategies) obtained a higher mean attitude score of 57.78, with a standard deviation of

11.63, for jigsaw teaching strategy and a mean attitude score of 44.29, with a standard deviation of 8.13, for geoboard strategy. The control group (lecture method) obtained a mean attitude score of 43.46, with a standard deviation of 10.12. Table 3 showed that students taught geometry with jigsaw strategy scored the highest marks followed by students taught with geoboard and lecture method respectively.

Hypothesis Two: There is no significant difference in the geometry mean attitude scores among students taught with jigsaw teaching strategy, geoboard instructional strategy and lecture method.

Table 4: ANOVA Comparison of Pretest Scores of Jigsaw Teaching Strategy, Geoboard Strategy and Lecture Method

	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	112.643	2	56.321	1.005	.367
Within Groups	16032.167	286	56.057		
Total	16144.810	288			

P>0.05

The ANOVA comparison of the groups as shown in Table 4 indicated non-significant difference, $F(2, 286) = 1.005$, $P(0.367) > 0.05$. This implies that there is no significant difference in the pre-test scores of the three groups compared. Hence, the hypothesis was tested with ANOVA.

Table 5: ANOVA Comparison of Posttest Scores of Task-Based Teaching Strategy, Self-Regulated Learning Strategy and Lecture Method

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	12596.144	2	6298.072	62.060	.000
Within Groups	29024.147	286	101.483		
Total	41620.291	288			

P<0.05

A significant difference was found between the group taught with jigsaw teaching strategy, geoboard strategy and lecture method as shown in Table 5, $F(2, 286) = 62.060$, $P(0.000) < 0.05$. Therefore the null hypothesis was rejected. Thus, there is a significant difference in the Geometry mean attitude scores among students taught with jigsaw teaching strategy, geoboard strategy and lecture method.

Table 6: Scheffe’s Post-Hoc Test to Compare Jigsaw Teaching, Geoboard Strategy and Lecture Groups on Students’ Attitude

Dependent Variable	(I) Instructional strategies	(J) Instructional strategies	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig.	95% Confidence Interval	
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Attitude posttest score	Jigsaw Strategy	Geoboard Strategy	13.489*	1.439	.000	9.95	17.03
		Lecture	14.315*	1.455	.000	10.74	17.90
	Geoboard Strategy	Jigsaw Strategy	-13.489*	1.439	.000	-17.03	-9.95
		Lecture	.826	1.462	.852	-2.77	4.42
	Lecture	Jigsaw instruction	-14.315*	1.455	.000	-17.90	-10.74
		Geoboard	-.826	1.462	.852	-4.42	2.77

*. The mean difference is significant at the 0.05 level.

The Scheffe’s post-hoc analysis shows that there is a significant difference between the mean attitude scores of students taught geometry with Jigsaw teaching strategy and those taught with geoboard strategy, in favour of Jigsaw teaching strategy. There is also a significant difference between the mean attitude scores of students taught geometry with Jigsaw teaching strategy and those taught with lecture method, in favour of Jigsaw teaching strategy. There is no significant difference between the mean attitude scores of students taught geometry with geoboard strategy and those taught with lecture method. Table 6 shows that out of the three methods, Jigsaw teaching strategy proved most effective on students’ attitude towards geometry.

Discussion of Findings

The study revealed that there is a significant effect of jigsaw teaching strategy, geoboard strategy and lecture method on students’ attitude towards geometry. This is evident on the higher posttest attitude scores of students taught geometry with jigsaw teaching strategy, geoboard strategy and lecture method as shown in Table 1. As shown in Table 1, students’ posttest attitude scores greatly increased after treatment compared to their pretest attitude scores. This increment is as a result of treatment with the use of jigsaw teaching strategy, geoboard strategy and lecture method. Therefore, it can be concluded that jigsaw teaching strategy, geoboard strategy and lecture method have significant effect on students’ attitude towards geometry. This finding corroborate the work of Achor and Kalu (2014) conducted research on increasing students’ attitudes toward chemistry by employing an error analysis approach in the teaching of practical

chemistry and found that there was no significant difference in the experimental group's mean attitude between males and girls ($P = 0.327 > 0.05$). The finding of the study also agree to that Akaazua, Bolaji, Kajuru, Mu, Musa, and Bala (2017) studied the Effect of Concrete Manipulative Approach on Attitude, Retention, and Performance in Geometry in Benue State, Nigeria and found that the Concrete Manipulative Approach was not gender biased in attitude formation,

Again, the study revealed that there is a significant difference in the geometry mean attitude scores among students taught with jigsaw teaching strategy, geoboard strategy and lecture method. Furthermore, the difference between the mean attitude scores between students taught geometry using geoboard strategy and lecture method was insignificant. The difference in the mean attitude scores among the three groups may be as a result of the different teaching methods adopted in each group. The teaching methods adopted may have promoted students' development of positive attitude towards geometry concepts more than the other. As indicated in Table 5, students taught geometry with jigsaw teaching strategy outscored those taught with geoboard strategy and lecture method. This suggests that students in jigsaw teaching group may have been more active during the teaching and learning process due to their resolution of practical learning tasks. This contributed to the higher attitude scores. The low attitude scores of students in the lecture group is as a result of the passive involvement of students during the teaching and learning process since teachers pass their knowledge to students. This finding supports that of Celik (2018) who studied the impact of activity-based learning on sixth-grade students' achievement and attitudes toward mathematics who found that both groups' academic achievement grew in a beneficial way. On the other hand, whereas students' attitudes toward activities declined dramatically in the experiment group, they grew in the control group. This finding disagrees with that of Jegede and Awodun (2015) who reported that there was a substantial difference in students' attitudes toward Physics in the experimental and control groups, with the experimental group outperforming the control group.

Conclusion/Policy Recommendation

Based on the findings that arising, the study conclude that the implementation of jigsaw teaching strategy gives students' a positive attitude towards geometry than the lecture method. Geoboard instructional strategy enhance students' attitude towards geometry than the lecture method. The researcher therefore recommend the adoption of jigsaw teaching strategy by mathematics teachers when there is special need to students' positive attitude towards geometry. Mathematics teachers should attend workshops to get acquainted with innovative instructional strategies. And Mathematics teachers should strive to ensure that students are active during instruction as this will help to stimulate their interest in having a better attitude towards geometry.

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